

INCHILDHEALTH Study

FOLLOW THE FOOTSTEPS TO LEARN MORE ABOUT IT

WHAT IS A STUDY?

A study is when you try to learn more about something or discover something new.

WHAT ARE WE LOOKING AT IN THE STUDY?

We want to study the impact of indoor air quality in classrooms on children's health.

WE NEED YOU! DO YOU KNOW WHY?

Your school has agreed to take part in the study. Now we would like to invite you and your friends to join. We can't do it without you!

WHO WILL PARTICIPATE?

5 schools from Vienna and their students aged 6 to 13 years are participating in the study.

HOW LONG DOES THE STUDY LAST?

The study will take place in the 2023/2024 school year.

WHAT DO YOU HAVE TO DO?

Answer a few questions and collect samples with us. You will do this together with your friends and teachers.

WHAT IS GOOD ABOUT THIS STUDY?

Thanks to your participation, we can understand the quality of indoor air. After that, we can gather ideas for better air in schools.

ARE THERE ANY BAD THINGS ABOUT THIS STUDY?

No, there aren't any. But if you don't feel comfortable, you can talk to us at any time and we will find a solution.

FINISH

WHO SHOULD I ASK IF I HAVE ANY QUESTIONS?

You can ask your parents or teachers, who will discuss your concerns with us.

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GIVE US YOUR CONSENT

My participation in the study

I have read the information on the front page and understand what I will do in the study.

I will participate in the following activities:

- * workshop at school
- * filling out questionnaires
- * collecting samples

Name of the child

The following information will be collected from me:

- * my age
- * my gender
- * my student number

Signature of the child

I agree to participate in the INCHILDHEALTH study during the 2023/2024 school year.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Name of the legal guardian

I agree that our child will participate in the INCHILDHEALTH study at school.

Any questions? Contact us:

name of contact person:

www.InChildHealth.eu

Signature of legal guardian

Signature: _____

Date: _____

